

EFFECTIVE JUDICIAL PROTECTION FOR THE LAWFUL EXERCISE OF DISCRETIONARY POWERS

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Abstract

This paper highlights the role of the judiciary in ensuring the rule of law in the Republic of North Macedonia, particularly in the lawful exercise of discretionary powers by all holders of public office. The study examines the need to strengthen anti-corruption policies in order to meet the standards of Chapter 23 for North Macedonia's accession to the European Union.

Within this paper, the subject of research is the discretionary powers of holders of public office. Initially, the paper defines discretionary powers, their types, elements, and the principles for applying discretionary powers. The paper identifies institutional weaknesses due to improper use of authority, information, and documentation. This is followed by an analysis of court decisions focusing on administrative judicial control over the limits of such powers. By presenting decisions of the Administrative Court for the period 2015–2025, the paper emphasizes the need for a proportionality test when exercising discretionary powers. Finally, it concludes that there is a need to establish a standard model that North Macedonia must adopt in order to reduce risks and prevent potential adverse consequences arising from the misuse of discretionary powers.

Keywords: rule of law, discretionary power, judicial protection, proportionality test, binding nature of final court decisions

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of modern democracies is based on the responsible exercise of power. In the modern political community, the hallmark of democracy is the guarantee of freedoms and rights, establishing a rule of law state with zero tolerance for abuses. The division of power into legislative, executive, and judicial aims primarily to prevent the concentration of power. However, it is primarily necessary to pass laws that not only declaratively proclaim rights but can also be functionally applied. The executive power is obliged to implement them through the administrative bodies, and the judicial power, by resolving disputes, implements them in practice to protect the rights of citizens.

This paper highlights the role of judicial power in ensuring the rule of law in the Republic of North Macedonia in relation to the lawful practice of discretionary powers by all holders of public office. By combining normative analysis with empirical methods to explore different legal grounds of final court judgments (case studies) of the Administrative Court (hereinafter: the Court), this paper identifies procedural violations in

the exercise of discretionary powers. By presenting cases from the administrative judiciary through the test of proportionality, a comparative analysis of court decisions for the period 2015-2025 is made. The main goal of this empirical research is to detect weaknesses, all with the aim of reducing risks and preventing possible undesirable consequences due to abuses in discretionary powers.

2. DISCRETIONARY POWERS THROUGH THE PRISM OF NATIONAL LEGISLATION AND CASE LAW

2.1 Legal-Philosophical Conception of Discretionary Powers

In his work *The Laws*, Plato discusses the development of state systems in history and explains the relationship between justice and power (Plato, 1971:521). He believes that the one who enforces the law and is consistent in respect must be authorized to implement and supervise the application of the laws. Unfair conduct is unacceptable from those in power who are obliged to apply the laws and interpret them correctly (Rawls, 1997:269).

Weber created a systemic theory of power and explains it as a "factual situation in which the expressed will is an order from those who rule and influences the actions of others" (Weber, 1976:446). Labović, through the etymological roots and theoretical teachings of the phenomenological forms of power, provides an analysis of the conceptual distinction between the terms power, politics, might, and authority (Labović, 2006:40). In political practice, the division of power into legislative, executive, and judicial branches is generally accepted. However, Loewenstein (as cited in Kitanovski, 1996:30) believes that when dividing power and functions, the control over politics is of essential importance, and this is ensured not only by the division of power but also by applying the principles of political responsibility.

Political might endangers other principles of the rule of law: the principle of legality, free elections, the exercise of public functions, the public interest, an independent judiciary, and the constitutionally presumed legitimacy of the state. The question arises of how the rule of law state can develop its own defence system, and how the rule of law state can be protected "against the state" (Kambovski, 2005:580). Academician Kambovski believes that for self-defence, the state "must embed strong and autonomous instruments of protection, above all, through an independent and powerful judiciary and other institutions for the protection of human rights that will act as a counterweight to the criminal aspirations of political powerful figures" (Kambovski, 2005:59).

The idea of democracy appears in the text of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms in three different forms that are used as standpoints and interpreted in concrete cases from the practice of the European Court. It appears primarily as a principle contained in the Preamble, which requires all members of the Convention to interpret the articles in accordance with the general spirit of the Convention as an instrument designed to maintain and proclaim the ideals and values of a democratic society (Omejec, 2013:1089).

According to legal science, the rule of law and the rule of law state seemingly appear to be synonyms and imply issues of constitutionality and judicial control of constitutionality, but etymologically they have a different origin and are not identical, although they have common points. The 'rule of law' is a term that originates from England and was developed by Anglo-American legal theory, while the genesis of the term 'rule of law state' is from German legal thought. Professor of Constitutional Law Svetomir Škarić elaborates on the two concepts and states that the concept of the rule of law state is

based on natural law, more precisely on human freedoms and rights, and is associated with liberal democracy and less with the functions of power and formal legality. On the other hand, the rule of law state implies the functioning of state power and formal legality, and less the quality of the laws. Therefore, the Constitution of the Republic of North Macedonia adopted the term rule of law as a fundamental value from the aspect of limiting power and respecting human rights and freedoms.

In the modern British constitution, the term 'rule of law', according to Dicey, implies the sovereignty of Parliament, and for form, the rule of law is the supremacy of the law (Dicey, 1889:303). The rule of law implies respect for the rights of the citizen: the right to property, existential rights, to work, to a salary, to social and health insurance, and freedoms, ensured security, all in the sense that power should be limited by existing judicial control.

When it comes to the rule of law state, Škarić refers to the concept from three aspects, stating that the concept of the rule of law state encompasses a material, formal, and social aspect (Škarić, 2014:36). The material aspect was developed by Robert von Mohl, the formal by Friedrich Stahl, and the social by Heinz Nauler (as cited in Škarić, 2014:37). The material aspect takes into account the primacy of law over state power. First, this means guaranteeing human rights and freedoms, and personal freedoms and rights; second, ensuring favourable conditions for the development of civil society; and third, determining the legal limits of state power. The formal aspect emphasizes, first, the inviolability, the formal characteristics of constitutionality and legality, and not the goals of the state and the content of laws and other regulations and by-laws. The rule of law state is valued depending on how much constitutionality and legality are realized as formal-legal categories, and as a result, the rule of law state can be a mere formal legality, without the natural-law content of the laws and the guarantee of freedoms and rights.

2.2 Concept, Definition, and Types of Discretionary Powers

According to Recommendation No. R(80)2 of the Committee of Ministers, discretionary powers are defined as "powers that give administrative bodies a certain degree of freedom regarding the decision to be made, allowing them to choose the one they consider most appropriate from several legally acceptable decisions" (Council of Europe, 1980). Additionally, Recommendation CM/Rec(2007) of the Committee of Ministers stipulates that "the administration shall not be arbitrary when using discretionary powers" and that "when the administration uses discretionary powers, it shall maintain a proper balance between any negative effects that its decisions have on the rights or interests of private persons and the goal they pursue" (Council of Europe, 2007).

Discretionary powers represent a right that the law grants to institutions (most often to the heads of institutions or their authorized officials) from the public sector to decide freely in situations that are also determined by law. Legal science first views discretionary powers as a legal norm contained in a general legal act (law, by-law), which must be applied to a real individual case and then transformed into a concrete administrative act (resolution, decision, etc.) (Gjorgievski & Vrglevski, 2023:11).

Discretionary powers can be distinguished in relation to who uses them as:

- Executive discretionary powers (held by the holders of public office within the executive power and exercised by issuing an executive decision).
- Administrative discretionary powers (used by public officials when resolving cases in administrative procedures and deciding on the rights, obligations, and legal interests of citizens).
- Judicial discretionary powers (referring to the powers of public prosecutors and courts – most often referring to the right of free judicial discretion).

Discretionary powers can also be distinguished according to the way they are set up, i.e., formulated: Legal acts may contain legal norms with the so-called explicit or express discretionary powers, which clearly instruct the body to make a free decision (discretionary power) when choosing one of the two or more options contained in the norm. Such discretionary powers are most often found in substantive laws that provide concrete rights for citizens and regulate special administrative procedures in which those rights can be exercised.

2.3 Discretionary Powers in National Legislation

In the Macedonian legal system, discretionary powers are directly mentioned in the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (LPCCI), the Criminal Code (CC), the Law on General Administrative Procedure (LGAP), and the Law on Administrative Disputes (LAD). The essence of discretionary powers is the freedom of the official when making a specific decision on behalf of a public institution. The legislation does not directly define discretionary powers, but it nevertheless recognizes them as a legal institute and prescribes how they should be applied by the administration and controlled by the Court. In the legislation, the phrases "discretionary powers" and "resolving by free assessment" are used synonymously.

Measuring the proportionality and reasonableness of the administration's decisions, especially discretionary decisions, is closely related to the purpose of the authorization, which officials can initially perceive in the provisions of the law from which the discretionary power emanates. Specifically, laws usually begin with an article describing the purpose of the law, which should be reflected throughout the text of the law and during its application in specific cases. The words "purpose," "subject," or "function" are commonly used.

The LPCCI recognizes discretionary powers as one of the greatest risks for corruption. Under the term "risk of corruption," a definition of corruption is given, which means abuse of office, public authorization, official duty, or position to gain benefit, directly or through an intermediary, for oneself or another, thus encompassing the concepts of passive corruption and active corruption (LPCCI, 2019, Article 8). The Law contains definitions of several terms: public interest, public authorization, and the term official duty, with the aim of ensuring the lawful, independent, impartial, ethical, responsible, and transparent implementation of the law.

For the exercise of discretionary powers, it is determined that every official is obliged to make decisions conscientiously, taking into account all the facts and circumstances of the specific case and the principle of legality and fairness (LPCCI, 2019, Article 63). A natural or legal person dissatisfied with a decision made on the basis of discretionary power and who believes that the decision was made due to corruptness can

submit a petition to the State Commission. The SCSC is obliged to consider the petition and, within 30 days from the date of receipt, inform the natural or legal person about the action taken on it. Furthermore, it must publish statistical data on the submitted petitions on this legal basis on its website twice a year.

The special form of incrimination is unconscientious work in the service from Article 353-v, paragraph 4 of the Criminal Code (1996). Academician Kambovski gives a definition of "unconscientious conduct" which consists of a violation of a special regulation or the abuse of discretionary powers of the executor, or the omission of due supervision in formal and material abuse (Kambovski,2016:1065). Another way of obviously unconscientious conduct is the conclusion of harmful contracts, a conflict of interest, as well as the consequences of this unconscientious conduct, which exceed the degree of carelessness, sloppiness, or misdemeanour liability in the professional ethics of officials. Consequences of the act include obtaining property benefit, some material or immaterial benefit for oneself or another, and the executor must be proven to have had intent, more precisely, awareness that the law was violated, i.e., the official did not act in accordance with their duties. Punishment for the negligent execution of this form of the act is also provided for in paragraph 5 of the same article.

The LGAP, in Article 5, paragraph 3, stipulates that if the public body is authorized by law to decide by free assessment, the administrative act must be adopted within the limits of the law that grants the authorization, in accordance with the purpose for which the authorization was given, and must be specifically reasoned (2019). In this context, the concept of the LGAP emphasizes that public bodies should be service-oriented in order for citizens to efficiently and effectively exercise their rights, but on the other hand, they are also obliged to protect the public interest.

Other laws in the Macedonian legal system grant discretionary powers to public sector institutions. Elements of discretionary powers exist in decision-making on rights that citizens can exercise. Viewed through the prism of case law, great unprofessionalism is also noted in the commissions formed by the Pension and Disability Insurance Fund (Case *Metastaza*, 2012), as well as in the commissions of the Health Insurance Fund. This is because they are obliged to give an expert opinion on the diagnosis of the disease, the stage of the diseases, and the projection of diagnosing the disease, and not to engage in the interpretation of laws.

Independent institutions that monitor the work of public bodies in practicing discretionary powers within their competencies include: the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption, the Commission for Prevention and Protection against Discrimination, the State Audit Office, and the State Commission for Protection against Discrimination.

2.4 Law Created by European and National Case Law

European administrative procedural law is based on administrative principles (rule of law, transparency, proportionality, impartiality, and efficiency), on European administrative standards that are not determined statically but are developed on the basis of formally prescribed standards (hard law), case law (case law, judge-made law), and on the basis of good practices (soft law) (Koprić, 2014:12). European courts have an active role in interpreting rules and standards and imposing innovations on national courts. Therefore, in 2018, the Law on Courts was intervened again to make the practice of the European Court mandatory; specifically, an addition to Article 18 establishes that "when making a

decision, the court is obliged to apply the positions expressed in the final judgments of the European Court of Human Rights" (Law on Courts, 2006).

2.5 Judicial Protection and Control of Discretionary Powers

Regarding judicial control, there is a difference as to whether it is carried out over concrete acts, over general acts, or whether the responsibility of administrative employees is decided.

- If a general act of the administration is the subject of control, the Constitutional Court of the Republic of North Macedonia decides on its constitutionality and legality.
- If the legality of concrete administrative acts is decided, the authority to annul it is within the jurisdiction of the administrative judiciary.

The Court exerts direct influence on the administration through the authorizations issued by administrative bodies when deciding on the rights and obligations of citizens in the administrative procedure. This is done by annulling the act and instructing the body to adopt a new one in accordance with the court's indications, and in a dispute with full jurisdiction, even by deciding to resolve the administrative matter itself. This achieves two goals: the first is the protection of the rights and interests of citizens from arbitrary and self-willed actions of administrative bodies, and the second refers to the protection of the legal order by removing acts with which administrative bodies violate the principle of legality.

Regarding the control of discretionary powers, the Court can decide on the legality and the limits of the authorization of the public body that decided according to free assessment – the discretionary right (LAD, 2019, Article 6).

However, an administrative dispute cannot be conducted over the correct application of free assessment by a public body (discretionary power) when adopting an individual administrative act, but it can be conducted over the legality of such an act and the limits of such an authorization. This means that the Court is obliged to determine whether the public body was authorized to apply free assessment and whether it adhered to the limits of the given authorizations on that occasion.

To illustrate the case law, we will refer to final court decisions of the Court with the legal basis of control of the lawful use of discretionary power. Decision-making on lawsuits is related to the test of proportionality – *stricto sensu* (Grimm, 2016:171–172)⁶.

1. Initially, the legitimacy is examined—whether the decision was made by a competent body and whether the decision is aimed at achieving the purpose of the law, whether it is lawful and legally sound.
2. Then, it is determined whether there is excessive interference of the public authority in the rights provided by national legislation and the convention. This step represents a balanced analysis where the benefits of the decision made are

⁶ Traditionally, the test of proportionality is applied to measures undertaken by the administration (especially the police) which restrict the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens. It was established in the 19th century by the Administrative Court of Prussia, and later adopted and developed by the Federal Constitutional Court of Germany. This method has a tremendous influence on European legal systems.

measured against the losses from the restriction of certain rights. All of this must be proportionate and necessary in relation to the public interest and essential in a democratic society.

3. Only if the benefits exceed the burden imposed on the rights will it be considered suitable (Möller, 2023:8).

To illustrate judicial control over discretionary powers, an analysis of the Administrative Court's case law reveals systemic violations in three key areas: procedural jurisdiction, the right to a reasoned decision, and the misapplication of substantive rights.

1. The first case study concerns the discretionary powers of a plaintiff, a former President of the Republic, who challenges the decision of 1. Jurisdictional & Procedural Violations: The Court consistently annuls decisions where strict procedural standards or constitutional boundaries are ignored. In Judgment URP no. 39/2019, it annulled a decision by the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption (SCSC) against the President of the Republic, ruling that Article 87 of the Constitution grants exclusive jurisdiction for presidential accountability to the Assembly. Similarly, Judgment U-5 no. 1452/2018 protected the separation of powers by voiding an Assembly decision to dismiss SCSC members because the Government's involvement infringed upon legislative independence. Procedural strictness was further enforced in Judgment U-5 no. 380/2025, where the Court annulled the election of a Constitutional Judge because the Judicial Council failed to assess candidates' work results or follow voting protocols required by Article 98 of the Law on the Judicial Council.

2. Lack of Reasoning & Transparency: Failure to provide adequate reasoning—a core requirement of the LGAP and Article 6 of the ECHR—is a frequent ground for annulment. In Judgment U-5 no. 316/18 (national security certificates), the Court ruled that withholding classified evidence from the defence prevented a lawful assessment, citing the ECHR precedent *Ljlatifi v. Republic of Macedonia*. The judgment underscored that Article 6 mandates the principle of "equality of arms," requiring that the plaintiff be given a genuine opportunity to challenge the state's assertion that national security is endangered. Consequently, the Court found that denying the party access to the decisive evidence created a procedural imbalance that violated their Convention rights. Likewise, in Judgment U-5 no. 729/14, it found that administrative bodies arbitrarily denied free legal aid without explanation, failing to consider material facts such as the applicant's minor children.

3. Substantive Rights & Social Justice: Judicial intervention is particularly robust when discretionary power affects the welfare of children and vulnerable families. In Judgment U-5 no. 729/14 (free legal aid), the Court expanded the interpretation of the law to include divorce proceedings, reasoning that the protection of the applicant's minor children supersedes rigid administrative lists. Similarly, in Judgment U-5 no. 180/2015, it prioritized protection against domestic violence over bureaucratic hurdles. Furthermore, Judgment U-4 no. 343/20 addressed a discriminatory interpretation regarding parental allowance for a third child, where the administration excluded an adopted child by focusing solely on the "physical act of childbirth." The Court annulled this, establishing that under Article 113 of the Family Law, adoption equates to birth. The ruling emphasized that the state's objective is to support child-rearing and family values, not merely biological

reproduction, thereby strictly prohibiting discrimination against adoptive families. Finally, regarding environmental rights, Judgment USPI no. 2/2024 established that the Government's failure to adopt the National Ambient Air Protection Plan since 2018 directly violated the constitutional right to a healthy environment.

CONCLUSION

We can conclude that states strive to strengthen their position, primarily for the sake of the security of citizens and the fight against crime and the mafia. The fight against terrorism, organized crime, and corruption, as well as the need for the development and maintenance of transnational prevention, are especially important for international law. Legal certainty and protection from the unlawful use of discretionary powers are ensured through the impartial application of the rights and interests of natural and legal persons, regardless of the status and characteristics of the parties. Therefore, consistent provisions for clear discretionary powers are necessary, as is the use of control mechanisms over the implementation of laws. It is necessary to strengthen institutions in the direction of autonomous instruments of protection. Also, raising awareness of the importance of the lawful practice of discretionary powers is very important. The delivery of quality services by the administration and the correct application of discretionary power are ensured through the test of proportionality.

From the analysis of the court decisions, it was concluded that the thorough reasoning and justification of the decisions, i.e., the acts of the public administration, contribute on the one hand to limiting the potential abuse of discretionary powers for corrupt purposes, and on the other hand, to strengthening the legal remedy with which they can potentially be challenged, and thus to the implementation of much more effective control. The relationship between the administration and the judiciary is independent; they are functionally and organizationally autonomous, and the judiciary retains the role of a controller over the legality of the acts and the operation of the administration. The principles of law and the judicial and constitutional-judicial protection based on them are, for now, confirmed as the most suitable instruments for approaching the great ideas and aspirations for freedom, justice, and truth in a contemporary civil and conflicted society.

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